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TO ENHANCE THE SOLUBILITY OF CURCUMIN BY SOLID SELF-MICROEMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM (SMEDDS).

Mrudula H. Bele^{*}, Ashpak A. Shaikh, Sanket G. Paralkar

Dept. of Pharmaceutics, NDMVP's college of Pharmacy, KTHM Campus, Gangapur Road, Nashik.

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ABSTRACT

This study was performed to develop and characterize a novel solid self- microemulsifying drug delivery system of class IV drug curcumin by spray drying method using Aerosil 200 as the solid carrier for the purpose of solubility enhancement of curcumin. Solubility of curcumin was determined in various vehicles, including oils, surfactants and co-surfactants. The compatibility study was performed by IR and DSC. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed to identify the most efficient self-emulsification region. The optimized liquid SMEDDS for curcumin formulation contained oil capryol 90, surfactant kolliphor TPGS and co-surfactant PEG 400 in the ratio 3:1:1. The optimum liquid SMEDDS consisted of 4% curcumin, 60% capryol 90, 20% kolliphor TPGS and 20% PEG 400. Solid SMEDDS were also evaluated for flow properties like angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index, bulk density and tapped density. The curcumin liquid and solid SMEDDS formulation rapidly formed fine oil-in-water microemulsion with mean globule size 153 ± 7.4 nm and 169 ± 8.2 respectively. The drug formulated in the solid SMEDDS was quickly and completely dissolved ($\geq 90\%$) within 120 min, both in 0.1N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 dissolution media, whereas crude curcumin powder was significantly less soluble. The solubility of S-SMEDDS in distilled water was enhanced 151.68 fold and 170.87 fold when determined by UV and HPLC respectively, whereas aqueous solubility of crude curcumin was $0.694 \mu\text{g/ml}$. This study demonstrates that self-microemulsifying drug delivery system results in significant improvement in solubility and dissolution of very poorly water soluble drug curcumin.

Corresponding author

Ashpak A. Shaikh.

Dept. of Pharmaceutics,
NDMVP's college of Pharmacy,
KTHM Campus, Gangapur Road, Nashik
ashpakshaikh29792@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Curcumin is a naturally occurring golden yellow compound found as the main constituent in the rhizome of the plant *Curcuma longa*. Curcumin is the principal curcuminoid of the popular Indian spice turmeric, which is a member of the ginger family Zingiberaceae. It is estimated that 2% - 5% of the turmeric is curcumin. The molecular formula of curcumin is $C_{21}H_{20}O_6$ and it has a molecular weight of 368.39. The melting point is about 170–175°C. Curcumin is soluble in ethanol and concentrated acetic acid. Curcumin shows a weak green fluorescence in ethanol. Furthermore, curcumin is soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, methanol, ethyl acetate, dimethyl sulfoxide, and acetone. Curcumin is insoluble in water and diethyl ether. It is also light-sensitive and unstable in alkaline solutions. Commercially available curcumin is generally composed of about 77% curcumin, 17% demethoxycurcumin, and 3% bisdemethoxy-curcumin.^[2]

Chemical Structure of Curcumin.

Pharmacologically, curcumin has been used as a traditional medicinal agent in Ayurvedic medicine for ~6000 years. The pharmacokinetic, pharmacodynamic, and clinical pharmacological properties of curcumin have been extensively studied over the past six decades. These studies have demonstrated that curcumin functions as an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-atherosclerotic; inhibits scarring, cataract, and gallstone formation; promotes wound healing and muscle regeneration; prevents liver injury and kidney toxicity; and exerts medicinal benefits against psoriasis, diabetes, multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer, HIV disease, septic shock, cardiovascular disease, lung fibrosis, arthritis, and inflammatory bowel disease. Recently, curcumin has garnered interest as a potential anticancer agent, for both chemopreventive and chemotherapeutic purposes. In vitro cell culture and in vivo animal studies have suggested that curcumin may be able to treat numerous types of cancer, including breast cancer, colon cancer, kidney cancer, liver cancer, leukaemia, basal cell carcinoma, prostate cancer, rhabdomyosarcoma, and melanoma. Curcumin can effectively inhibit almost every major stage of carcinogenesis, including transformation, initiation, promotion, invasion, angiogenesis, and metastasis.^[4] Also curcumin is well tolerated at levels up to 12 g/day for 3–4 months in clinical settings.^[4]

Curcumin has variety of uses but it belongs to BCS Class IV drug and due to this reason it cant able to exert the desired pharmacological action, So the aim of this research work is to formulate S-SMEDDS so that solubility of curcumin get enhance and it will able to exert desired pharmacological action. In spite of these attractive properties of curcumin, information on the therapeutic efficiency of curcumin has been limited, partly due to its poor oral bioavailability (<2%). The reason for poor bioavailability of this agent within the body includes the following:

1. Poor absorption which is due to the low solubility of curcumin in water or in gastrointestinal tract. Wahlstrom and Blennow first reported negligible amounts of curcumin in blood plasma of rats after oral administration of 1g/kg of curcumin showed that curcumin was poorly absorbed from the gut.
2. High rate of metabolism. Once absorbed, curcumin is subjected to conjugations like sulfation and glucuronidation at various tissue sites. Hydrolysis of plasma samples with glucuronidase showed that 99% of curcumin in plasma was present as glucuronide conjugates.
3. Systemic elimination or clearance of curcumin from the body is also an important factor, which determines its relative biological activity. The elimination half-life of orally administered curcumin (2 g/kg) in rats was reported to be 1.7 ± 0.5 hours.^[5]

The solubility of curcumin in water especially at acidic and physiological pH is extremely low (11ng/mL). It is hydrolysed rapidly in alkaline solutions and readily decomposed when exposed to bright light, high temperature or oxidative conditions^[6]. Also intestinal first-pass metabolism and intracellular accumulation played a role in poor permeability of curcumin. Curcumin was poorly permeable with a P (app) (A → B) value of $2.93 \pm 0.94 \times 10^{-6}$ cm/s. P(app) value in (B → A) study was found out to be $2.55 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-6}$ cm/s, thus ruling out the role of efflux pathways in poor oral bioavailability of curcumin. Based on its poor aqueous solubility and permeability, curcumin can be classified as a BCS class IV molecule.^[7]

SOLUBILITY

Solubility of a drug is one of its important physico-chemical properties. More attention has been paid to the aqueous solubility since water is the unique solvent of biological systems. It is obvious that a drug should be reached to its receptors in the body through the aqueous and non-aqueous media. The chance of a low water soluble drug to be appeared in the market place is very low and nearly 40 % of the drug candidates fail to reach higher phases of the drug trials simply because of their low water solubility^[8]. The term 'solubility' is defined as maximum amount of solute that can be dissolved in a given amount of solvent. It can also be defined quantitatively as well as qualitatively. Quantitatively it is defined as the concentration of the solute in a saturated solution at a certain temperature. In qualitative terms, solubility may be defined as the spontaneous interaction of two or more substances to form a homogenous molecular dispersion. A saturated solution is one in which the solute is in equilibrium with the solvent. Almost more than 90% drugs are orally administered. Drug absorption, sufficient and reproducible bioavailability, pharmacokinetic profile of orally administered drug substances is highly dependent on solubility of that compound in aqueous medium. More than 90% of drugs are approved since 1995 have poor solubility. It is estimated that 40% of active new chemical entities (NCEs) identified in combinatorial screening programs employed by many pharmaceutical companies are poorly water soluble. Drug absorption, sufficient and reproducible bioavailability and/or pharmacokinetic profile in humans are recognized today as one of the major challenges in oral delivery of new drug substances. Orally administered drugs on the Model list of Essential Medicines of the World Health Organization (WHO) are assigned BCS classifications on the basis of data available in the public domain. The 130 orally administered drugs on the WHO list, 61 could be classified with certainty. 84% of these belong to class I (highly soluble, highly permeable), 17% to class II (poorly soluble, highly permeable), 24 (39%) to class III (highly soluble, poorly permeable) and 6 (10%) to class IV (poorly soluble, poorly permeable). The rate and extent of absorption of class II and class IV compounds is highly dependent on the bioavailability which ultimately depends on solubility. Due to this major reason solubility enhancement is one of the important parameters which should be considered in formulation development of orally administered drug with poor aqueous solubility^[9]. Table 1 listed different solubility terms used in the USP and Figure 1 shows Biopharmaceutical classification system.

Table 1: Different solubility terms used in the USP^[10].

Descriptive terms	Parts of solvent required for one part of solute	Solubility range (mg/ml)	Solubility assigned (mg/ml)
Very soluble	less than 1	>1000	1000
Freely soluble	from 1 to 10	100-1000	100
Soluble	from 10 to 30	33-100	33
Sparingly soluble	from 30 to 100	10-33	10
Slightly soluble	from 100 to 1000	1-10	1
Very slightly soluble	from 1000 to 10,000	0.1-1	0.1
Practically insoluble	more than 10,000	<0.1	0.01

Figure 1: Biopharmaceutical classification system^[11].

In above figure 1 x-axis shows the volume (ml) required to dissolve the highest dose strength of the parent drug at the lowest solubility over the pH 1–7.5. A parent drug is considered ‘highly soluble’ when the highest dose strength is soluble in <250 ml water over a pH range of 1–7.5, in which 250 ml reflects the so-called FDA glass of water. The y-axis shows the permeability, which is defined by various in vivo or in vitro assays, and a permeable drug is the one associated with 90% oral bioavailability or 90% absorption as assessed by urinary excretion data.^[11]

Figure 2: Strategies to modify BCS class of drug^[12]

Figure 2 shows the strategies for improvement in absorption for different drug molecules based on the biopharmaceutics classification system. Drugs in class I (high permeability (HP) and high solubility (HS)) are generally well absorbed and lead optimisation programs are focussed on progression of compounds in this class. Although possible, improvement in intestinal permeability (i.e. promoting apparent shifts in drug class from class III (high solubility (HS), low permeability (LP)) and IV (low solubility (LS), low permeability (LP)) to class I, dashed arrows in figure) are not well characterised in terms of toxicity and are generally avoided. In contrast the use of formulation design to promote an apparent shift in drug properties from class II (low solubility (LS), high permeability (HP)) to class I is possible and becoming more commonplace.^[12]

LIPID FORMULATION CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM

Due to the large number of possible excipient combinations that may be used to assemble lipid based formulations and self-emulsifying systems in particular, a classification system (Lipid Formulation Classification System-LFCS) was established by Pouton in 2000 and recently updated (2006) to help stratify formulations into those with similar component parts. The LFCS classifies lipid-based formulations into four types according to their composition and the possible effect of dilution and digestion on their ability to prevent drug precipitation.

The main purpose of the LFCS is to enable *in vivo* studies to be interpreted more readily, and subsequently to facilitate the identification of the most appropriate formulations for specific drugs, i.e. with reference to their physicochemical properties. Table 2 indicates the fundamental differences between Type I, II, III and IV formulations. Whilst the defining properties of each type are easy to understand, as yet there are few studies which link the LFCS with *in vitro* or *in vivo* performance. Many of the marketed products are Type III systems but this group is particularly diverse as a result of the wide variation in the proportions of oily and water-soluble materials used. To indicate this issue in previous publications this group has been further divided into Type IIIA and Type IIIB, to distinguish between formulations which contain a significant proportion of oils (Type IIIA) and those which are predominantly water-soluble (Type IIIB). The distinction between Types IIIA and IIIB was based arbitrarily, as a starting point for discussion, on the proportions of typical excipients in formulations. At present the sub-classification of Types III formulations is ill-defined, particularly when one considers that a Type III formulation could contain 3–5 excipients, including water-insoluble and water-soluble surfactants, as well as water miscible cosolvents. In the immediate future it will be important to establish *in vitro* performance criteria which can be determined experimentally to distinguish between various Type III formulations, because this group is likely to contain formulations which have very different performance characteristics. The rate of crystallisation of drug from the prototype Type IIIB formulation is much more rapid than from the Type IIIA formulation, a property which is likely to affect the physical form of the drug in the intestine and, as a consequence, affect the rate of absorption of the drug. Discussions are under way to establish performance criteria which can be accepted broadly across the industry, to improve the tools available to formulators and perhaps also to facilitate engagement with regulatory agencies on matters related to lipid-based products.^[13]

Type I formulations, which are simple solutions of the drug in triglycerides and mixed glycerides, are a reasonable starting point in the search of a lipid based formulations.

Type II formulations that add a lipophilic surfactant (HLB <12), are employed when greater drug solubilizing capacity is desired in a SEDDS formulation.

Type IV contains a greater ratio of hydrophilic to lipophilic components than the former. While type IV formulations are associated with more facile self-emulsification and smaller lipid droplet size than type III, they carry a greater risk of drug precipitation as the hydrophilic components may separate from the oil phase during dispersion in the GIT leading to loss of drug solubilizing capacity.^[14] The following Table 2 shows Composition and salient features of various types of SEDDS formulations.

Table 2: Composition and salient features of various types of SEDDS formulations:

Constituents/Attributes	Type I	Type II	Type IIIA	Type IIIB	Type IV
Triglycerides or mixed glycerides	100%	40-80%	40-80%	<20%	-
Water insoluble surfactants	-	20-60%	-	-	0-20%
Water soluble surfactants	-	20-40%	20-50%	30-80%	Water soluble surfactants
Hydrophilic cosolvents	-	-	0-40%	20-50%	0-50%
Particle size of dispersion (nm)	Coarse	100-250%	100-250%	50-100%	-
Significance of aqueous dispersion	Limited Importance	Solvent capacity Unaffected	Some loss of solvent capacity	Significant phase changes and potential loss of solvent capacity	-
Significance of digestibility Characteristics	Crucial requirement Non-dispersing, requires digestion	Not crucial, but is likely to occur SEDDS without water-soluble components	Not crucial, but may be inhibited SEDDS/ SMEDDS with water-soluble components	Not required, but is unlikely to occur SMEDDS with water-soluble components and low oil content	-
Advantages	GRAS status; simple; excellent capsule compatibility	Unlikely to lose solvent capacity on dispersion	Clear to almost clear dispersion; drug absorption without digestion	Clear dispersion; drug absorption without digestion	Oil-free formulation based on surfactants and cosolvents Good solvent capacity for many drugs; disperses to micellar solution
Pitfalls	Formulation has poor solvent capacity, unless drug is highly lipophilic	Turbid o/w dispersion	Possible loss of solvent capacity on dispersion; less easily digested	Likely loss of solvent capacity on dispersion	Loss of solvent capacity on dispersion; may not be digestible

On the basis of the water solubility of components, SEDDS can be classified as

Non-Water Soluble Component Systems:^[16]

These systems are isotropic mixtures of lipids & lipophilic surfactants having HLB value less than 12 that self-emulsify to form fine oil in water emulsion in aqueous medium. Self-emulsification is generally obtained at a surfactant level above 25% w/w. But at a surfactant level of 50-60% w/w the emulsification process may be compromised by formation of viscous liquid crystalline gels at the oil/water interface. This system is also known as Type-II SEDDS according to lipid formulation classification System (LFCS). Poorly water soluble drugs can be incorporated in SEDDS & encapsulated in capsules (hard or soft gelatin) to produce convenient single unit dosage forms. These systems offer advantages like they are able to generate large interfacial areas which cause efficient partitioning of drug between oil droplets and the aqueous phase. They can overcome the slow dissolution step typically observed with solid dosage forms.^[16]

Water Soluble Component System.^[16]

These systems are formulated by using hydrophilic surfactants with HLB more than 12 and co solvents such as ethanol, propylene glycol and polyethylene glycols. Type III SEDDS are commonly known as self-microemulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS). Type III formulations can be further divided into type III A and Type III B formulations in order to identify more hydrophilic forms. In Type IIIB, the content of hydrophilic surfactants and co solvents is increased and lipid content is reduced. The distinction between SEDDS and SMEDDS formulation is commonly based on particle size and optical clarity of resultant dispersion. Thus SEDDS formulations typically provide opaque dispersions with particle size greater than 100 nm while SMEDDS disperse to give small droplets with particle size less than 100 nm and provide optically clear or slightly opalescent dispersions. SEDDS and SMEDDS have played an important role in the improvement of solubility as well as bioavailability of drugs with poor aqueous solubility. An example of the marketed SMEDDS formulation is Neoral Cyclosporine formulation in which corn oil, derived mono, di and triglycerides were used as lipid phase, cremophor RH 40 as surfactant, propylene glycol and ethanol as co solvent along with α -tocopherol as an antioxidant. Neoral spontaneously forms a transparent and thermodynamically stable dispersion with droplet size below 100 nm when introduced into an aqueous medium. SEDDS may be solid or liquid in nature and they may be formulated into tablets, capsules, pellets, solid dispersions, microspheres, nanoparticles or dry emulsions.^[16]

MATERIALS & METHODS

Curcumin was procured from Aptuit Laurus, Hyderabad. Capryol 90 procured from Gattefosse India Ltd. & Abitec, Captex 500, Captex 200, Campul MCM procured from Gattefosse India, Kolliphor (HS 15, RH 40 EL and TPGS) obtained as a gift sample from BASF Laboratory, Mumbai. PEG 400, olive oil, Linseed oil, Procured from Modern Chemicals, Nashik. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preformulation Study:

Preformulation testing is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms of a drug substance alone and when combined with excipients, with an objective to generate information useful to the formulator in developing a stable and bioavailable dosage form.

Drug Authentication:**Melting Point:**

Melting point of the drug was determined by using capillary tube method.

FTIR Spectroscopy:

FTIR spectrum was taken and sample was scanned over wavenumber range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. The instrument used was Bruker spectrophotometer.

UV Spectroscopy:

10mg of curcumin was weighed accurately and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved in methanol and the volume was made up with methanol. This was the stock solution of curcumin (100 μ g/ml). 10ml from above solution was taken and diluted up to 100ml with methanol, this was standard stock solution of curcumin (10 μ g/ml). Appropriate quantities of aliquots (2ml to 10ml) of the standard stock solution were taken in 10ml volumetric flasks. These were then diluted with methanol to make solutions of concentration of 2 to 10 μ g/ml. The spectrum of curcumin was scanned over wavelength range of 800-200nm and λ max was determined. The absorbance of solutions were recorded at this wavelength by using the UV/Visible spectrophotometer. The calibration curve was plotted by taking absorbance on Y-axis and concentration of drug on X-axis.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Analysis:

Thermograph of curcumin was obtained using Shimadzu DSC-60 using aluminium pans. Nitrogen was purged through cooling unit. Indium standard was used to calibrate the DSC temperature. The samples were hermetically sealed in aluminium pans and heated at constant rate of 10°C/min over a temperature range of 30 to 230°C. Inert atmosphere was maintained by purging nitrogen at the flow rate of 70ml/min.

Solubility:

Pure curcumin not detected by UV spectroscopy as it has very poor solubility and also due to sensitivity of UV spectrophotometer. For the comparison of solubility of pure curcumin and curcumin loaded SMEDDS it is necessary to establish correlation between method of analysis or determination of solubility hence solubility of pure curcumin and curcumin loaded SMEDDS Formulation were determined by both UV Spectroscopy and High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).

Solubility of Curcumin in Water by HPLC:

For the determination of solubility 10mg of drug was added into distilled water and kept for 24hrs at room temperature with occasional stirring. The solution was filtered through membrane filter and filtrate was collected. Then solubility was determined by HPLC analysis.

Table 3: Parameters for aqueous solubility of curcumin by HPLC analysis.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Values
1	Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: Water: Methanol (50:40:10)
2	pH of mobile phase	3
3	Sample volume	20µl
4	Flow rate	1.0ml/min
5	Pressure	10-11MPa
6	Runtime	12.03 min
7	Wavelength	430nm

Solubility of Curcumin in Different Solvent by UV:

For the determination of solubility, excess amount of drug (40mg) was added into media/solvents and kept for 24hrs at room temperature with occasional stirring. The solution was filtered and filtrate was taken. Suitable dilution were prepared and analysed by using Shimadzu UV-2450 double beam spectrophotometer.

Selection of Excipients:**Determination of Solubility of Curcumin in Oils, Surfactants and Co-surfactant:**

The solubility of curcumin in various vehicles, including oils (olive oil, linseed oil, captex 500, captex 200, capmul MCM, capryol 90), surfactants (tween-20, tween60, labrasol, cremophor EL, kolliphor EL, kolliphor TPGS, kolliphor RH40, and kolliphor HS15) and co-surfactants (ethyl alcohol, PEG 400, and isopropyl myristate) was determined by the shake flask method. An excess amount of curcumin (100mg) was added to each cap vial containing 5 ml of the vehicles.

After sealing, the mixture was magnetically stirred in order to facilitate proper mixing of curcumin with the vehicles. Then mixtures were then centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 15min. The supernatants were collected into glass vials and after suitable dilution with methanol analysis was carried out with UV-visible spectrophotometer to find the concentration of drug.

Selection of Surfactants (Emulsification Study):^[17]

Different surfactants were screened to evaluate their propensity for emulsification of aqueous phase. For each surfactant 10ml of 10%w/v solution was prepared in preselected oil phase and distilled water was subsequently added to each of this solution in increasing order until the system becomes cloudy. The study was performed in triplicate.

Selection of Co-surfactants (Emulsification Study):

Different combinations like kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: PEG400, kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: PEG200, kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: ethyl alcohol, kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: isopropyl myristate were tried and evaluated visually in specific ratios for ability to self-emulsify in water. Co-surfactant with best emulsification capability was selected.

Selection of Surfactant and Co-surfactant Ratio (Km) by Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagrams:^[17]

The Km ratio was optimized for various ratios by water titration method. Mixtures containing oil phase capryol 90 and a combination of surfactant and co-surfactant; kolliphor TPGS and PEG 400 in different ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) were titrated with water and the concentration of water at which turbidity-to-transparency and transparency-to-turbidity transition occurred was derived from the weight measurement. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed using Chemix software to determine the boundaries of the microemulsion regions corresponding to the selected optimum ratios of combination vehicles for developing curcumin-SMEDDS. After the identification of emulsion region in the phase diagrams, the emulsion formulations were selected at desired component ratios and selection of emulsion region from phase diagram was based on the fact that solution remains clear even on infinite dilutions.

Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies:**By FT/IR:**

The drug excipients compatibility study was carried out by FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra of drug and excipients physical mixture were taken and compared with the pure drug. FTIR spectrum was observed for fundamental peaks retained and any modification occurred in the fundamental peaks. Presence of any new peak was also observed.

By DSC:

The drug excipients compatibility study was carried out by DSC. Different formulation's DSC thermograms were taken and compared with the pure drug. Formulation's DSC thermograms were observed for fundamental peaks retained and any modification occurred in the fundamental peaks. Presence of any new peak was also observed.

Preparation of Self-Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS): ^[22]

The phase diagram indicated that Smix ratio 1:1 shows higher self-emulsifying region than other Smix ratio 1:3, 1:2, 2:1 and 3:1. It was also observed that in case of Smix 3:1 during water titration there is gel formation which requires more vigorous shaking for emulsification to occur, which may not be acceptable for self-emulsification criteria. Based on this different formulation with Smix ratio 1:1 were prepared with the increasing concentration of drug to achieve the highest drug loading into liquid SEDDS. These components were accurately weighed and mixed using a magnetic stirrer. Depending on solubility, the formulation amount of curcumin was dispersed into the mixture of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant. Then, the components were mixed by gentle stirring and vortex mixing at 37°C until curcumin was dissolved completely. Then the mixture was sealed in glass vial and stored at room temperature until used.

Table 4: Maximum possible drug loading of liquid SMEDDS.

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity in mg			
		C1	C2	C3	C4
1	Curcumin	300	350	400	450
2	Capryol 90	6000	6000	6000	6000
3	Kolliphor TPGS	2000	2000	2000	2000
4	PEG 400	2000	2000	2000	2000
Total (mg)		10300	10350	10400	10450

Preparation of Curcumin Loaded SMEDDS:

Liquid SMEDDS were formulated using optimised ratio of surfactant and Cosurfactant with oil and then curcumin was loaded in different concentrations on magnetic stirring.

Characterization of Liquid SMEDDS:**Self-Emulsification Efficiency:**

The self-emulsification performance of the curcumin-SEDSS was studied using the USP30 dissolution apparatus II (paddle type). Liquid curcumin-SEDSS formulation equivalent to 50mg was placed in 900ml distilled water. Gentle agitation was provided by a paddle rotating at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and a rotating speed of 75rpm. The self-emulsification performance of the formulation was visually assessed according to the grading system that is reported by Khoo et al.

Measurement of Mean Globule Size: ^[23]

SEDSS 1ml was diluted with 50ml water and gently mixed. The mean globule size and zeta potential of resultant emulsion were determined with Zetasizer (Ver. 6.20, MAL1051945, Malvern) at scattering angle 90° . All measurements were performed at temperature 25°C . Sample was analysed in triplicate.

Percent transmittance (%T):

Percent transmittance is determined to check the transparency of formulation. The percent transmittance of the formulation is measured at wavelength 428nm using UV spectrophotometer by using distilled water as blank.

Robustness to Dilution:

Formulations were subjected to 50, 100, 1000 and 3000 fold dilution with distilled water. The resultant diluted emulsions were monitored for any physical changes such as (coalescence of droplets, precipitation or phase separation) after 24hr storage.

Solidification of Liquid Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System:**Spray Drying of Liquid SEDDS:**

Aerosil 200 (2.66g) was suspended in 400ml ethanol by sonication for at least 10min and about 12.00gm of the optimized liquid SEDDS containing 510.6mg of curcumin was added with constant stirring until a good suspension was obtained. The suspension was then spray dried with Labultima spray dryer (LU 222advanced) under the following condition.

Table 5: Parameters of spray drying.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Condition
1	Inlet temperature	60°C
2	Outlet temperature	35°C
3	Inlet high	75°C
4	Outlet high	50°C
5	Feed pump rate	2ml/min
6	Aspirator speed	45%

After the completion of drying process, fraction of dried S- SEDDS were collected from different parts of spray dryer i.e. drying chamber, first cyclone separator and collector attached to it.

Characterization of Solid SEDDS (S-SEDDS):

Yield of Spray Dried Product:

The percentage yield of S-SEDDS was calculated by using the following formula,

$$\% \text{ yield} = \text{material recovered from spray dryer} / \text{weight of (liquid SEDDS+ Aerosil 200)} \times 100.$$

Flow Properties of Spray Dried Product:

Bulk Density and Tapped Density:^[10]

Both untapped bulk density (q_u) and tapped bulk density (q_t) were determined by USP 30 method. A specific amount of powder blend was introduced into 10ml measuring cylinder. Then the weight of powder blend was determined by subtracting the weight of empty measuring cylinder from the final weight of measuring cylinder. The cylinder was allowed to fall on to a hard surface at the rate of 300falls/min for 500 taps, the volume was noted and then additional 750taps were given and again volume was noted. q_u and q_t were determined by following formulae;

$$q_u = m/v_u$$

$$q_t = m/v_t$$

Where m = mass of the sample, and v_u & v_t = untapped & tapped volumes respectively.

Carr's Compressibility Index:^[10]

An important measure that can be obtained from bulk density determination is the percent compressibility.

$$C = q_t - q_u / q_t \times 100$$

Where q_u = untapped bulk density, and q_t = tapped bulk density

Hausner's Ratio:^[10]

A similar index has been determined by Hausner.

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = q_t / q_u$$

Where q_u = untapped bulk density, and q_t = tapped bulk density

Angle of Repose:^[10]

The angle of repose of the powder blend was determined by funnel method. The funnel was adjusted in such a way that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the heap of the powder. The diameter of the powder cone was measured and angle of repose was calculated by using following formula

$$\tan \Theta = h/r$$

' h ' is height of the powder cone and ' r ' is radius of the base of the powder cone.

Total Curcumin Content:

The amount of curcumin present in S-SMEDDS was determined by dissolving S-SMEDDS equivalent to 10 mg of curcumin into 10ml of methanol and after suitable dilution with methanol UV absorbance was measured at 426 nm.

Globule Size Determination:

SEDDS formulation 1gm was diluted with 100 ml distilled water in a beaker with constant magnetic stirring. The average globule size and zeta potential of microemulsion from solid SEDDS were assessed with Zetasizer (Ver. 6.20, MAL1051945, Malvern). Sample was analysed in triplicate.

In-vitro Dissolution Study:^[22]

In-vitro dissolution was carried out to study the effect of S-SMEDDS formulation on the dissolution behaviour of curcumin. Drug release studies from S-SEDDS were performed using USP dissolution apparatus II (Lab India-DS 8000) using 900ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and 0.1N HCl as a medium at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The speed of the paddle was adjusted to 75rpm. Curcumin-loaded S-SEDDS (equivalent to 10mg of curcumin) was added in dissolution media. At predetermined time intervals an aliquot (5ml) of the sample was collected, filtered and analysed for the content of curcumin by UV spectroscopy. An equivalent volume (5ml) of fresh dissolution medium was added to compensate for the loss due to sampling to maintain sink condition.

Table 6: Parameters for in-vitro dissolution study.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Specifications
1	Dissolution apparatus	USP II Paddle type
2	Dissolution medium	Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)/ 0.1N HCl
3	Volume	900ml
4	Temperature	$37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$
5	Rotation speed	75rpm
6	max	428nm

Solubility of S-SMEDDS:

The solubility of S-SMEDDS in distilled water was determined. An excess amount of S-SMEDDS (100mg) was placed in glass bottles containing 10ml of water. The bottles were kept for 24 hrs at room temperature with occasional shaking. At the end of this period the solutions were filtered through membrane filter and the filtrate was collected into dry containers. The solutions were analysed by UV/VIS double beam spectrophotometer and HPLC. The concentration of S-SMEDDS was calculated using calibration curve of curcumin.

Result & Discussion**Preformulation Study:****Description:**

The sample of curcumin was found to be orange-yellow in colour and has characteristic odour.

Melting point:

Melting point of the drug was found to be $179\text{-}186^\circ\text{C}$ using capillary tube method. Readings were taken in triplicate and average was taken. (Reported M.P. $175\text{-}183^\circ\text{C}$)

IR Spectroscopy:

The FT-IR spectra of curcumin were determined. In FT-IR spectra of the mixtures of Drug and Excipients there are no alteration as compared to pure curcumin. A spectrum is shown in figure which confirms drug sample was authentic.

Figure : 2 ATR Spectrum of Curcumin.**UV Spectroscopy:**

Maximum absorbance of curcumin was found to be at 428nm this is characteristic property of curcumin in its pure form hence it can be confirmed that obtained sample was authentic.

Figure 3: UV spectrum of curcumin in methanol.

□□ Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Analysis:

Thermogram of curcumin shows sharp exothermic peak at 174.3°C attributed to its melting point. Endothermic peak of fusion of curcumin is sharp denoting crystallinity of the drug sample.

Figure 4 :DSC thermogram of Curcumin.

Solubility:

Pure curcumin not detected by UV spectroscopy as it has very poor solubility and also due to sensitivity of UV spectrophotometer. For the comparison of solubility of pure curcumin and curcumin loaded SMEDDS it is necessary to establish correlation between method of analysis or determination of solubility hence solubility of pure curcumin and curcumin loaded SMEDDS Formulation were determined by both UV Spectroscopy and High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).

Solubility by HPLC:

Solubility is mentioned in table 7.

Table 7: Concentration and area values for curcumin by HPLC.

Sr. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Area
1	1	69988
2	2	147097
3	3	229848
4	4	292407
5	5	386771
6	Unknown	45666

Figure 5: Calibration curve of curcumin by HPLC.**Selection of Excipients:****Determination of Solubility of Curcumin in Different Oils, Surfactants and Co-surfactants:**

Solubilities of curcumin in different oils and surfactant solutions are shown in Table 8. Results revealed that Capryol 90 oil was the only oil in which the drug showed the desired solubility for dosage development.

Table 8: Solubility study of curcumin in different oils.

Sr. No.	Oils	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	Olive Oil	0.165
2	Linseed Oil	0.00365
3	Capmul MCM	0.3588
4	Captex 200	0.1945
5	Captex 500	6.726
6	Capryol 90	23.904

Table 9: Solubility of curcumin in different surfactants.

Sr. No.	Surfactants	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	Kolliphor EL	13.503
2	Kolliphor TPGS	20.489
3	Kolliphor RH40	08.163
4	Kolliphor HS15	21.540
5	Cremophor EL	16.690
6	Labrasol	0.995
7	Tween 20	19.225
8	Tween 80	19.017

Table 10: Solubility of Curcumin in different Co-surfactants.

Sr. No.	Co-surfactant	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	PEG 400	19.562
2	Ethyl Alcohol	0.1779
3	Isopropyl Myristate	0.00365

Selection of Surfactant (Emulsification Study):

From all the eight surfactants (kolliphor EL, kolliphor TPGS, kolliphor HS 15, kolliphor RH 40, cremophor EL, labrasol, tween 20 and tween 80) screened for their propensity for emulsification of aqueous phase. Kolliphor TPGS showed immediate and complete emulsification with lowest amount required. Based on drug solubility and compatibility with drug and oil, kolliphor TPGS with HLB 13-14 was selected as a surfactant because it showed best emulsification efficiency and additionally permeability enhancing property.

Selection of Co-surfactants (Emulsification Study):

The components were selected for further studies depending on maximum drug solubility in oil phase, surfactant and cosurfactant and ability to self-emulsify for the particular combination of this vehicle with each other. Different combinations like kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: PEG400, kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90:PEG 200, kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: ethyl alcohol, kolliphor TPGS :capryol 90: isopropyl myristate were tried and evaluated visually in specific ratios for ability to self-emulsify in water. Among all these combinations a system containing kolliphor TPGS (surfactant), capryol 90 (oil) and PEG 400 (co-surfactant) gave clear, transparent, stable and rapidly self-emulsification. During water titration there is gel like mass formation with the kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: PEG 200 combination which required more vigorous shaking for emulsification to occur, which may not be acceptable for self-emulsification criteria. Hence this kolliphor TPGS: capryol 90: PEG 400 combination of excipients was used for further study.

Selection of Surfactant to Co-surfactant Ratio (Km ratio) by Construction of Pseudo-ternary Phase Diagram:

The surfactant to co-surfactant ratio plays a crucial role in the characteristics of self -emulsification and hence it was optimized using different ratios of surfactant (kolliphor TPGS) and co-surfactant (PEG 400).

Table 11: Composition of oil, surfactant and co surfactant (Smix 1:1).

Sr. No.	Capryol 90 (% w/w)	Kolliphor TPGS (% w/w)	PEG 400 (% w/w)
1	90	5.0	5.0
2	80	10	10
3	70	15.0	15.0
4	60	20.0	20.0
5	50	25.0	25.0
6	40	30.0	30.0
7	30	35.0	35.0
8	20	40.0	40.0
9	10	45.0	45.0

Figure 6: Pseudo-ternary phase diagram of capryol 90 with Smix 1:1 constructed using CHEMIX Software.

Table 12: Composition of oil, surfactant and co surfactant (Smix 1:2).

Sr. No.	Capryol 90 (% w/w)	Kolliphor TPGS (% w/w)	PEG 400 (% w/w)
1	90	5.0	5.0
2	80	10.0	10.0
3	70	15.0	15.0
4	60	20.0	20.0
5	50	25.0	25.0
6	40	30.0	30.0
7	30	35.0	35.0
8	20	40.0	40.0
9	10	45.0	45.0

Figure 7: Pseudo-ternary phase diagram of capryol 90 with Smix 1:2 constructed using CHEMIX Software.**Table 13: Composition of oil, surfactant and co surfactant (Smix 1:3).**

Sr. No.	Capryol 90 (% w/w)	Kolliphor HS 15 (% w/w)	PEG 400 (% w/w)
1	90	5.0	5.0
2	80	10.0	10.0
3	70	15.0	15.0
4	60	20.0	20.0
5	50	25.0	25.0
6	40	30.0	30.0
7	30	35.0	35.0
8	20	40.0	40.0
9	10	45.0	45.0

Figure 8: Pseudo-ternary phase diagram of capryol 90 with Smix 1:3 constructed using CHEMIX Software.

**Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies:
By FT/IR:**

Figure 9: FT/IR spectra of curcumin with all Excipients.

By DSC

Figure 10: DSC thermogram of curcumin with all Excipients.

Thermogram of curcumin mixed with all excipients (Formulation) shows sharp endothermic peak at 172.84°C attributed to its melting point which reveals that there is no any incompatibility.

Preparation of Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS):

Table 14: Drug loading in liquid SEDDS.

Sr. No.	Time (hrs)	C1	C2	C3	C4
1	0	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear
2	24	Clear	Clear	Clear	Crystal out
3	48	Clear	Clear	Clear	Crystal out
4	72	Clear	Clear	Clear	Crystal out
5	96	Clear	Clear	Clear	Crystal out
6	120	Clear	Clear	Clear	Crystal out

Characterization of Liquid SEDDS:

Emulsification Efficiency and Precipitation Assessment:

Table 15: Emulsification efficiency and precipitation assessment.

Sr. NO.	Formulation	Speed of Emulsification	Clarity	Appearance	Precipitation
1	F1	Within 1 minutes	Clear	Slightly Yellowish in appearance	No

Determination of Mean Globule Size and Zeta Potential:

Table 16: Mean Globule Size and Zeta Potential of liquid SEDDS.

Sr. No.	Mean Globule Size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)
1	153±7.4	-6.89±0.41

The data of mean globule size shows reading 153 to 161nm which is within the range of microemulsion region. Hence it can be concluded that the formulation is microemulsifying. Zeta potential readings are below -20mV which shows that emulsion formed is stable.

Percent transmittance (%T):^[23]

Percent transmittance of formulation F4 was found to be 99.2% which is very close to that of water (100%T) means formulation is transparent in nature.

Robustness to Dilution:^[20]

The stable SEDDS formulations exposed to dilution with distilled water revealed all the formulations were found to be robust over wider degree of dilution without any signs of drug precipitation and phase separation.

Characterization of Solid SEDDS:

Yield of Spray Drying:

The percentage yield of S-SEDDS was calculated by using following formula,

$$\% \text{ yield} = \text{material recovered from spray dryer} / \text{weight of (liquid SEDDS+ Aerosil 200)} \times 100$$

$$= 5.70 / (10.400+2.21) \times 100$$

$$= 45.20 \% \text{ w/w .}$$

Flow Properties of Spray Dried Product:

Bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio of spray dried product is shown in table.

Table 17: Flow properties of spray dried product.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Results	Inferences
1	Bulk Density	0.407 gm/ml	-
2	Tapped Density	0.51 gm/ml	-
3	Angle of Repose	28.50	Good
4	Compressibility Index	20.19%	Fair
5	Hausner Ratio	1.253	Fair

Total Curcumin Content:

Total curcumin content was found to be 94.25%

Determination of Mean Globule Size and Zeta Potential:

The mean globule size and zeta potential of the reconstituted emulsion is presented in following table. From these results, encapsulating the liquid SEDDS in the Aerosil 200 by spray drying, which have not remarkable effect on globule size and zeta potential? The solid SEDDS preserved the self-emulsification performance of the liquid SEDDS.

Table 18: Mean Globule Size and Zeta Potential of S-SMEDDS.

Sr. No.	Mean Globule Size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)
1	169±8.2	-12.2±0.35

In-vitro Dissolution Studies:

In the self-emulsifying drug delivery system, the free energy required to form an emulsion was very low, thereby allowing spontaneous formation of an interface between the oil droplets and water. It is suggested that the oil/surfactant/co-surfactant and water phases effectively swell decrease the oil droplet size and eventually increase the release rate. In vitro drug release study was performed for S-SMEDDS formulation and is profiled in fig. The dissolution medium phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and 0.1N HCl was used to study the drug release. It is evident from the results that curcumin S-SMEDDS showed an improvement in the in vitro dissolution profile. Results revealed that curcumin S-SMEDDS showed more than 90% of curcumin release in 120min.

Table 19 : Dissolution study of S-SEDDS in 0.1N HCl.

Time (min)	% Drug Release (Mean ± SD)
5	10.13±0.78
10	19.576±0.77
15	30.743±0.57
20	42.23±0.95
25	51.58±0.37
30	56.776±4.42
45	68.992±1.16
60	74.96±1.43
90	84.97±1.65
120	95.06±0.56

Figure 11: Dissolution profile of solid SEDDS in 0.1N HCl.

Table 20: Dissolution study of S-SEDDS in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

Time (min)	% Drug Release (Mean ± SD)
5	15.216±1.45
10	26.025±0.86
15	40.49±0.99
20	56.55±0.49
25	65.174 ±1.33
30	73.84±0.62
45	84.08±1.14
60	91.465±0.48
90	93.611±1.10
120	96.123±0.29

Figure 12: Dissolution profile of solid SEDDS in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

Figure 13: Comparison of dissolution profiles of solid SEDDS powder in 0.1N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

Solubility of S-SMEDDS:

Solid SMEDDS powder consisting of oil, surfactant, co-surfactant and drug having the maximum solubility. After solubility study in distilled water, curcumin in S-SMEDDS resulted in significant improvement as compared with that of curcumin powder.

Table 21: Solubility of S-SMEDDS in distilled water.

Sr. No.	Formulation	Solvent	Analysed by	Solubility ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	P Value
1	PURE CURCUMIN	Water	HPLC	0.69	≤ 0.0001
2	S-SMEDDS	Water	HPLC	118.59	
3	S-SMEDDS	Water	UV	105.27	

CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel liquid SMEDDS consisting of capryol 90, kolliphor TPGS and PEG 400 as an oil phase, a surfactant and a co-surfactant, respectively, was formulated and further developed into a solid SMEDDS by a spray-drying technique using Aerosil 200 as the solid carrier. This solid SMEDDS preserved the self-emulsification performance of the liquid SMEDDS and gave a faster in vitro dissolution rate than the crude powder both in 0.1N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 dissolution media. Aqueous solubility of curcumin was enhanced to 151.68 fold and 170.87 fold determined by UV spectroscopy and HPLC method respectively. Considering the limitations associated with liquid SEDDS, a solid powder formulation should be a more acceptable form. Furthermore, results suggest that the solid SMEDDS could be considered and further evaluated for the oral delivery of lipophilic poorly soluble drugs for which an oral route of administration is desirable. This study demonstrates that self-microemulsifying drug delivery system results in significant improvement in solubility and dissolution of very poorly water soluble drug curcumin.

ABBREVIATIONS

S	-	SMEEDDS- Solid-Self microemulsifying drug delivery System.
SMEDDS	-	Self microemulsifying drug delivery system.
SEDDS	-	Self emulsifying drug delivery system.
DSC	-	Differential Scanning Calorimetry.
HPLC	-	High Performance Liquid Chromatography.
UV	-	Spectroscopy-Ultra-Violet Spectroscopy.
PEG 400	-	Polyethylene glycol.
TPGS	-	tocphery glycol succinate

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors do not report any conflict of interest.

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